

Application studies †

Zinc in AR ammonium chloride : A 1 M solution of AR NH_4Cl was prepared in triple-distilled water. From this solution, 2.5, 5.0 and 7.5 ml were used as the supporting medium alongwith 0.1 N NH_4OH . The effective NH_4Cl concentration in 25 ml system was 0.1, 0.2 and 0.3 M. The change in NH_4Cl concentration from 0.1 to 0.5 M in 25 ml system does not effect the Zn^{2+} peak. Polarograms were recorded, and by standard addition method the amount of Zn^{2+} in NH_4Cl was calculated. Pulse current read off the calibration plots gave results in accordance with the standard addition calculations. Ammonium chloride was found to contain 0.001 1% Zn^{2+} .

Leachable zinc in coal ash : Coal ash samples (obtained from Coal Survey Laboratory, Nagpur) were analysed for Zn^{2+} . A weighed quantity of coal ash was digested with concentrated HCl (10 ml) till complete silica was precipitated. After cooling, the white precipitate of silica was filtered off. The filtrate was taken up with water and made upto 10 ml. The polarogram of different aliquots of the sample solution was recorded against a blank. Qualitative and quantitative evaluation was done by standard addition procedure as well as by the calibration plot. The results were found to agree with both the methods. Three coal ash samples from three different regions were analysed, which were found to contain 2.9, 0.82 and 1.85 mg Zn^{2+} /kg.

Simultaneous determination of Cu^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} : Simultaneous determination was done in a synthetic mixture with the set polarographic conditions. A minimum of 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ of metal ion could be simultaneously determined with high precision.

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Ultra-trace Spectrophotometric Determination of Copper using 2-Thioquinaldinanilide

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THE reagent, 2-thioquinaldinanilide (TQA) has been utilised to develop a simple and rapid micro-chemical method for the detection and direct ultra-trace (ppb) determination of copper by spectrophotometry¹. The reagent is almost specific for copper in presence of almost all the metal ions. The method leaves no other choice for its wide range of applications towards a number of synthetic mixtures of composite form and standard samples with minimum deviation.

This newly synthesised reagent (TQA) offered several advantages over those proposed earlier²⁻⁵. High stability and easy solubility of the reagent in organic solvents, routine rapidity, wide pH and optimum range, and great interference limit with high selectivity are some of the major important highlights of the present method.

Experimental

A Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer with 1 cm glass cells were used for absorbance measurements. pH of the solutions were measured room temperature (27°) with a Elico LI-10 pH meter having all purpose glass electrodes.

A 0.1% (w/v) TQA¹ solution in ethanol was used. A 10% (w/v) triethanolamine hydrochloride (A.R.) was prepared. A buffer solution of pH 2.7 was prepared using sodium acetate—hydrochloric acid mixture. Solutions of diverse ions were prepared from their soluble salts and were standardised by conventional procedures. AnalaR grade solvents were used directly.

Procedure : To an appropriate amount of standard copper sulphate (10–100 μg cu) solution in a 25 ml standard volumetric flask was added a few drops of very dilute hydrochloric acid followed by 0.1% TQA solution (5 ml) and pure ethanol (7.5 ml) (pH 2.7), and the solution was diluted to 25 ml with water. Measure the absorbance of the blue-violet complex at 550 nm against water blank. Reagent blank prepared under identical conditions showed no absorbance, at this wave length. The unknown solution was processed similarly and its concentration was determined from the calibration curve.

Determination of copper in presence of V^{5+} , Mo^{6+} and W^{6+} : To a Cu^{2+} (0.1 mg) solution was

added vanadate (10 mg, V), molybdate (20 mg, Mo) and tungstate (5 mg, W) solutions. Then, 0.1 g each of hydroxylamine hydrochloride or ascorbic acid, oxalic acid and tartaric acid were mixed for reduction and masking, respectively, and the solution was slightly warmed and cooled. pH of the mixture was adjusted to 2.7. A 0.1% reagent (5 ml) was then added, cooled and transferred quantitatively into a 25 ml volumetric flask. The volume was made up with 50% alcohol at room temperature. Similarly, a solution was prepared without adding copper and used as the blank for absorbance measurement at 550 nm.

Determination of copper in presence of As^V , Sb^{III} , Bi^{III} and Pb^{II} : To a Cu^{II} (0.1 mg) solution was added arsenic (50 mg, As), antimony (50 mg, Sb), bismuth (50 mg, Bi) and lead (50 mg, Pb) nitrate solutions. Then, a 20% aqueous solution (5 ml) of triethanolamine hydrochloride and/or acetic acid were mixed for complexation and masking, and pH was adjusted to 2.7 with acetic acid. The solution (5 ml) was transferred and a 0.1% reagent solution added to it. The volume was made up to the mark with ethanol. Similarly, a solution blank was prepared for the absorbance measurement at 550 nm.

Determination of copper in alloy steel in presence of Fe^{III} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Mn^{II} and Cr^{III} : Steel sample (0.5 g) was dissolved in 3 M sulphuric acid (50 ml) and the solution was digested on a hot-plate with repeated addition of the acid. The solution was then treated with a few drops of concentrated nitric acid for complete digestion. The clear solution obtained was evaporated to a thick mass and then cooled, diluted with water (50 ml), filtered and washed with dilute acid. The filtrate and washings were cooled and transferred quantitatively into a 100 ml volumetric flask and the volume made up to the mark. Aliquots (5–10 ml) were taken, ascorbic acid solution (5 ml) added to it and pH adjusted to 2.7. The solution was transferred into a 25 ml volumetric flask, the volume made up to the mark with ethanol. A blank was prepared for the absorbance measurement at 550 nm.

Results and Discussion

The reagent (TQA) reacts with the metal to give a violet chelate at pH 0.5–6.5 in 1 : 1 alcohol-water or 1 : 1 acetone-water. The violet complex is non-extractable in solvents such as chloroform, benzene, carbon tetrachloride, isoamyl alcohol, methyl isobutyl ketone, dichloromethane and ether.

The composition of the Cu^{II} complex was found to be 1 : 3 (Cu–TQA) by continuous variation method and mole-ratio method. The complex was not extractable in non-polar phases and absorbed maximum at 550 nm.

The copper content was determined in presence of a typical class of refractory metals, base and toxic metals. The average of several determinations (Table 1) were almost same in 50% acetone medium.

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS OF SYNTHETIC MIXTURES AND STANDARD SAMPLES

Sample type	Cu present	Cu found
Refractory (V, Mo, W)	0.1 mg	0.099 ± 0.001 mg
Base and Toxic (As, Sb, Bi, Pb)	0.1 mg	0.099 ± 0.001 mg
Alloy Steel (BAS)	0.32, 0.10, 0.08 (%)	0.32, 0.10, 0.08 (%)

For the determination of alloy steels (Table 1) analysis in 50% acetone gave a better result, but required longer time for the development of a clear violet colour. The present method is a very fast, simple, accurate and direct for trace analysis of copper in mild steel and low alloys. Both the reagent and the method was found very sensitive for detection and estimation of Cu in presence of many metal ions.

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N-Bromophthalimide as an Oxidimetric Titrant. Some Direct Visual Titrations in Aqueous Acetic Acid Medium

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RECENTLY, *N*-bromophthalimide (NBP) has been developed as a typical oxidimetric titrant in aqueous acetic acid medium¹. In view of the facts that NBP is much stabler than NBS and is a better oxidant than the earlier developed oxidants of similar type we have considered it would be